

Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on upland rice

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We studied the response of upland rice TKM9 to *Azospirillum* inoculation.

A large number of efficient *Azospirillum* cultures were isolated from the root tissues of upland rice varieties.

Azospirillum lipoferum was the predominant species. Two isolates, C. 13 and IPI, have been recognized as the most efficient, with N₂-fixing abilities above 26 mg/g of energy source and acetylene-reducing activities (ARA) of the order of 350–400 nmol ethylene/ mg protein per h. The isolates were prepared as peat-based inoculants carrying about 10⁸ cells/g.

The crop was raised under upland conditions with graded levels of N and 40 kg P and K applied basally. Seed and

soil inoculation of *Azospirillum* were used (1 packet inoculum/20 kg seed and 8 packets/ ha).

Azospirillum inoculation significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). Response at 50 and 75 kg N was high. There was also a significant increase in the root surface area. Although both isolates performed well, C.13 was better. Grain yield with 75 kg N and *Azospirillum* inoculation was higher than with 100 kg fertilizer N. □

Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on grain and straw yields of TKM9. Coimbatore, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)		
	Uninoculated control	Inoculated with isolate C.13	Inoculated with isolate IPI	Uninoculated control	Inoculated with isolate C.13	Inoculated with isolate IPI
0	2.2	2.5	2.4	3.5	3.8	3.6
50	2.6	2.7	2.8	3.7	4.6	4.4
75	2.9	3.5	3.4	4.2	4.7	4.7
103	3.3	3.3	3.3	4.8	4.9	4.9
Mean	2.8	3.0	2.9	4.1	4.5	4.3
		CD (P = 0.01)			CD (P = 0.01)	
Treatment		0.5			0.1	
N		0.6			0.2	
Interaction		1.1			0.3	

Effect of leaf leachates of neem and sirish on the biomass production and pests of *Azolla pinnata*

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Azolla is an attractive host for a wide variety of pests, particularly snails (*Limnaea acuminata*), moths (*Nymphula*, *Pyralis*), and fungus (*Rhizoctonia solani*). We studied the effect of leaf leachates of several plants. Concrete pots with 1,964 cm² surface area were filled with 2 kg oven-dry soil plus 15 liters tap water. Fresh leaves (200 g) of *Albizia lebback* (sirish) or *Azadirachta indica* (neem) were suspended in pots inoculated with 20 g fresh green *azolla* plants, in 3 replications. The pots were placed in an open area with full sunlight for 6 wk during Apr–May at 40.5–42.0 temperature, and light intensity 105–115 klx. Half the biomass was harvested weekly. Insect, fungus, and snail

Influence of leachate of neem and sirish leaves on *azolla* biomass production. West Bengal, India.

Medium	Green biomass production (g/pot)					
	1st wk	2d wk	3d wk	4th wk	5th wk	6th wk
Leaf leachate of neem	56.5	84.0	168.2	246.3	259.0	242.2
Leaf leachate of sirish	59.0	78.0	152.3	85.2	25.5	–
Control	52.5	62.5	78.1	29.4	–	–
LSD (P=0.05)				7.0		

incidence was recorded during each harvest.

Plants cultured in sirish and neem leaf leachates were emerald green, with good growth and with no insects or snails up to the third week (see table). Control plants turned brown after 6 d, with poor growth leading to complete degeneration after 28 d. Seven insects and nine snails

were observed. With leachate of sirish leaves, 5 insects and 29 snails were found, leading to disappearance of the mass after 32 d, although the plant was still green. With leachate of neem leaves, only three snails and no insects were found and plants were green throughout the experiment. In no case were fungal symptoms observed. □

Efficiency of *azolla* as an organic N source for rice

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We laid out a 3-yr experiment at the Cropping Systems Research Centre during 1983–86 wet and dry seasons. Treatments were *azolla* alone, *azolla* in combination with nitrogenous fertilizers and N fertilizers alone, at